

April 2024 | 2nd Press Release

An event looking at automated solutions for sustainable construction and demolition waste management will take place on the University campus next month.

Organised by **RECONMATIC**, a Horizon Europe project led by a consortium of partners from academia and industry in the UK, EU and China, the event is aimed at sharing knowledge and expertise on sustainable construction and waste management and the digital transformation of the industry, following the very strict environmental targets to meet on the road to Net Zero. It will be hosted on our MediaCity UK campus building on Tuesday 7 May 2024.

This event is designed for professionals in the construction industry, aimed at all stakeholders linked to the life cycle of a construction asset, building or infrastructure and involved in construction and demolition waste management and circular economy at any point, such as manufacturers, developers, designers and contractors.

Organiser Juan Ferriz-Papi, lecturer and researcher at Salford, said:

“We have achieved good levels of construction waste recovery in the UK, but it is mostly in downcycling processes”

“The construction sector must make the transition to industry 4.0 and work towards interconnectivity, automation, machine learning and real-time data if we actually want to overcome the climate change crisis, achieve better and higher-value waste recovery and, subsequently, accomplish the proposed zero waste target by 2050.”

The activity will facilitate collaboration and synergies with other projects and initiatives running in the UK and contribute to shaping a common vision for the future.

The Open Day will develop different presentations and workshops for discussion about digital solutions for construction and demolition waste management, from digital twins to waste data management solutions, creating innovative and integrated systems for different digital technologies.

The UK partners participating in the event are the University of Salford, Morgan Sindall, BIMBox Ltd and the University of Manchester. Other entities are adhering and supporting it such as CIRIA and Zero Waste Scotland. As well, several European partners will participate in the presentations.

More information and free admission can be found [here](#).

The RECONMATIC project has been funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101058580 and by the UK Research and Innovation as part of the UK Guarantee programme for UK Horizon Europe participation. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the HORIZON-RIA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

